

Regional-Scale Debris-Flow Susceptibility Modelling. A case study in the Rocky Mountains

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Abstract—This study outlines the datasets and techniques employed to evaluate debris-flow runout susceptibility in the Valemout region, located in east-central British Columbia, Canada. The research spans an area of approximately 1200 km². A comprehensive landslide inventory exists for this region, which maps historical debris-flows by delineating both source zones and valley deposits. The inventory distinguishes between hillslope and channelized debris-flows, enabling separate modelling approaches for these phenomena. The outputs of both models were integrated to classify the region according to its vulnerability to debris-flow runout events. Landslide datasets independent of the training process were used for map validation and optimization. The results demonstrate a strong ability of the models to differentiate between areas likely to form debris-flow fans and regions outside the expected runout paths.

I. INTRODUCTION

Estimating the susceptibility of debris-flows is an important part of mitigation design, and consists of classifying the terrain according to the propensity to experience debris-flows. The goal of such studies is to provide a quantifiable relationship between the occurrence of debris-flows and environmental or physical factors observed on the slopes [1].

Despite the big effort made by researchers to date, modelling debris-flow susceptibility at a regional scale (including the initiation, transportation, and deposition zones) can be extremely challenging due to the complex and variable interactions existing during each event.

At regional scale, only few studies consider the debris-flow susceptibility as a combination of the likelihood to initiate a movement and propagate downhill [2, 3, 4]. In this study, we propose and describe a new framework to assess debris-flow susceptibility. We use a data-driven approach that combines both statistical and conceptual modelling by using a digital elevation model (DEM) and a landslide inventory as the main input data. We tested it over a large area in the Canadian Rocky Mountains, east central British Columbia (Fig. 1).

II. AVAILABLE DATA

A. Debris-flow inventory

The available landslide inventory, compiled from air photo interpretation, consisted of 1286 landslides classified into 11 types (debris-flow, rock avalanche, rotational slide, etc.) with three levels of certainty [5]. For this study, we used only the landslide features classified as “debris-flows”.

However, since under the general term of debris-flow there might be considerable differences in their behaviour, we manually reclassified each debris-flow of the inventory into either hillslope or channelized subtype [6]. To do so, we analyzed each landslide movement in relation to the morphology of the area on which it was triggered. This created two inventories: one consisting of 278 hillslope debris-flows, and the other of 68 channelized debris-flows. Most entries included the entire debris-flow body (source area, transportation zone and deposition zone). For some hillslope debris-flows, only the source area and zone of deposition were

delineated. As a final step, we reserved a group of isolated debris-flow deposit polygons for use in the validation.

Figure 1. Location map of the study area.

B. Digital elevation model (DEM) and environmental variables

A LiDAR-derived DEM served as the primary spatial reference throughout all phases of the experiment. This elevation map was created by manually merging LiDAR data collected between 2019 and 2021 at a resolution of 5 meters [5]. Based on the DEM, we also generated up to 49 derived maps to identify a suitable set of environmental variables for step 2 of the proposed framework (see Fig. 2). These derived maps represent commonly used indicators of terrain morphology, either resampled at different grid-cell resolutions or smoothed using a variable window-size filter [7].

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The proposed framework consists of a sequence of steps (Fig. 2) in which the debris-flow inventory is used to statistically train the models for both the initiation zones and potential runout. Other authors have recently used a similar approach [3, 8].

First, we applied logistic regression to generate a release area zone map specifically for hillslope debris-flows. This step was performed using the LAND-SUITE software [9] and a selection of 7 environmental variables from the original set of 49: cross-sectional curvature, longitudinal curvature, elevation range, sinusoidal slope, insolation time, stream power index, and topographic index. Next, we used the r.randomwalk tool with the obtained release area zone map to train and apply the runout model across the entire study area [9]. As a result, we produced a susceptibility map for hillslope debris-flow runout.

For channelized debris-flows, we assumed that movement typically triggers with the mobilization of debris within a confined valley or channel, where material is progressively supplied from

adjacent slopes. To identify potential source areas, we combined the hillslope debris-flow susceptibility map with downstream slope gradient values. As a result, we identified segments of the channel network most prone to channelized debris-flow initiation in areas where the hillslope debris-flow runout model reaches the channel and the downstream slope is between 15° and 24°, as suggested in the literature [10].

Figure 2. Simplified flowchart of the applied methodology. HAS = hillslope source area; HRS = hillslope runout susceptibility; CSA = channelized source area; CRS = channelized runout susceptibility.

The channelized debris-flow inventory was used to train the channelized runout-trajectory model and to simulate debris-flow trajectories, resulting in a map of the susceptibility of the channelized debris-flows to runout. Finally, the two susceptibility maps were combined to represent the likelihood of each pixel being crossed by one of these debris-flow sub-types, or both. To do so, we normalized the two original maps and then summed the normalized values.

Hillslope, channelized, and combined susceptibility maps were validated by using independent data from the debris-flow inventory. We followed a validation approach proposed by other authors in the past [8]. It consisted in building and comparing specific empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF) curves based on the runout susceptibility values predicted inside the validation polygons and in the rest of the study area. Figure 6 displays the ECDF curves for each region alongside the Kolmogorov–Smirnov D parameter. This statistic measures the maximum vertical distance between the ECDFs of susceptibility values within independent landslide polygons and those across the entire study area. A notably large D value indicates significant dissimilarity between the two functions, suggesting differences in susceptibility values within the validation inventory polygons compared to the broader region, as expected for a susceptibility map. Conversely, a very small D value suggests random sampling of susceptibility values by landslide polygons, pointing at potential biases in either the susceptibility map, the landslide inventory, or both. The advantage of using the ECDF lies in its ability to autonomously evaluate model performance, even with limited validation data and without the need for binary representation of the dependent variable.

IV. RESULTS

A. Hillslope debris-flow runout susceptibility

Following the r.randomwalk approach [11], we released 10 random trajectories from each cell enclosed in the source areas from the hillslope landslide inventory. The r.randomwalk tool keeps track of the angles of reach (Ω) corresponding to the moment when each trajectory leaves the boundaries of the deposition polygon. We collected all these values and obtained a correct fit with a Gaussian distribution model, where the peak can be found around the value of 29. This means that most of the simulated trajectories inside the landslide polygons stop when $\Omega = 29^\circ$. After that, we simulated debris-flow trajectories in the complete study area.

Fig. 4 we show the hillslope debris-flow runout susceptibility map. It was obtained by generating multiple trajectories from the hillslope source area model and using, as a break criterion, random values of the angle of reach (see r.randomwalk manual for more details). The legend and colours allow us to identify the areas where the relative probability of spatial occurrence of hillslope debris-flows is higher or lower than 0.5, with higher areas being the more susceptible to debris-flow runout.

Figure 3. Results of Hillslope Debris-Flow susceptibility modelling.

The plot in Fig. 5a shows the ECDF curves of the susceptibility values for both the validation dataset and the study area where D

Figure 5. From left to the right, validation results of Hillslope, Channelized and Combined debris-flow susceptibility models.

parameter = 0.45. This indicates that the model can recognize actual debris-flow susceptible areas. Therefore, such a large difference in susceptibility values reflects good modelling performance.

B. Channelized debris-flow runout susceptibility

According to the inventory, the areas mapped as channelized source areas equals a total of 5157 pixels, each of these releasing 100 random walks, for a total of 515,700 training trajectories. In this case, the distribution of the collected angle of reach values fits well with a log-normal distribution model, where the mode is observed around the value of 14. This means that most of the channelized debris-flow deposits in the study area will not stop until $\Omega = 14^\circ$.

Figure 4. Results of Channelized Debris-Flow susceptibility modelling.

As it can be observed in Fig. 5b, the difference between the curve of the validation dataset and that of the whole study area is significant, with D parameter = 0.80.

The map in Fig. 4 represents the runout susceptibility map of channelized debris-flows. Fan deposits generated from the steep incised valleys are evident. They display a runout zone reaching the main valley bottom, where principal infrastructure and urban settlements are located.

C. Combined debris-flow susceptibility map

For defining possible prevention and mitigation zones, we combined the results of both hillslope and channelized susceptibility maps to produce a single debris-flow runout susceptibility map (Fig. 6).

The resulting $D = 0.57$ value (Fig. 5c) demonstrates the model's capability to display higher relative susceptibility values within the validation zones than over the entire study area. Specifically, the plot highlights that only 25% of the validation data pixels have susceptibility values less than 0.5, compared to the entire study area, where more than 75% are at less than 0.5. Thus, this represents a valuable final step in the modelling.

Figure 6. Results of Combined Debris-Flow susceptibility modelling.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We produced three debris-flow runout susceptibility maps for a mountainous area, covering about 1200 km², located near Valemount, British Columbia, in the Canadian Rocky Mountains, where no regional susceptibility models previously existed. We applied statistical and conceptual modelling in the study area with high-resolution digital elevation model (5x5 m grid cells).

We considered two mechanical movements for the debris-flow types: hillslope and channelized. This duality was applied not only for the runout susceptibility modelling, but also for the source-area characterization. This allowed us to combine the resulting models into one final map product that ranks the terrain's susceptibility to either channelized or hillslope debris-flows or both. The two susceptibility models developed solely for hillslope and channelized debris-flows, as well as the final combined model, were validated by using independent sub-datasets, which showed good capabilities to detect potential debris-flow susceptible areas, even in places where no debris-flows have occurred or have yet been mapped.

The primary advantage of this methodology is its utility for regional analyses, since relatively little data are required for its application. Our approach can be used to identify areas most vulnerable to debris-flow runout and, conversely, those that are

less vulnerable to these phenomena. In addition, identification of intersections of the highest susceptibility zones with anthropogenic elements-at-risk will help to inform further detailed studies.

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